

THM@Sim4IA: Manual and automated next query prediction for user simulation

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1. Description

We took part in all three tasks of the Sim4IA shared task [1] and employed our different strategies over all of the tasks with the exception of the runs named `Nils`. Our code for our manual annotation tool as well as the automated runs can be found on GitHub¹.

1.1. Manual Runs

For manual runs we used a small tool to enable annotation off parts of queries and for pausing the annotation process and resuming the process whenever needed. Each query for each task was annotated separately. Annotators were presented the previous query or queries in case of tasks `A_2` and `B` as well as the titles of all interacted with documents. While coming up with next queries manually, we did not put any emphasis on reordering newly composed queries but instead kept them in the same order in which annotators came up with them.

For our run `Nils` we produced manual annotations for task `B` only. Here we looked at queries and results and tried to estimate what the searcher knows. The annotator tried to understand the query and results while using ChatGPT for help to give example queries. These example queries were then a point of orientation while writing the next queries.

The manual runs named `Nico` are based on users' previous searches as well as the documents that users interacted with. If the interacted with documents seemed relevant to the previous query, they were also considered in the composition of the new query.

The manual runs named `Julian` kept the style of the previous queries. For task `A_2` it was clearer how searches were based on each other. The existing queries oftentimes seemed to have not been influenced by the interacted with queries. We also considered query rewriting and included elements of the interacted with documents into new queries whenever fitting. For task `A_1` we tried to include clicked on documents. For task `B` we considered more context and tried to estimate what searcher learned from the answers given by the system.

The manual runs named `Ide` incorporated googling and translation. For task `A_1` the previous query was translated to German using Google or the Gemini web interface. Afterwards, a shortened version of the translated sentence was entered in Google to see search suggestions. These were then considered as next queries. Otherwise, the topics in the Google answers were considered when composing next queries. These next queries were then translated back to English and polished a bit using Gemini. For task `A_2` the same tactics was used as for `A_1` but this required less googling as this task was tackled afterwards. For task `B` the same strategy was employed as in `A_1`. The difference in this task was the reduced consideration of Google's results and more focus on the earlier queries.

Prompt ID	Prompt
Instruction	You are required to return EXACTLY %NUMOFQUERIES% potential next queries, NOTHING ELSE. Queries need to be distinct from each other. Order them in descending order by probability of them being the next query. Return these next %NUMOFQUERIES% queries as a Python-style list. These are the previous queries (preceded by "?") as well as the corresponding clicked on documents (preceded by ">");\n
Nils0	write new prompts fitting the subject, disregard results (marked by >) if they dont add to the context
Nils1	return new propts the user could serach try to follow the train of thought and redefine it every other new prompt
Nils2	return possible new prompts, mind the context and the possible train of thought followed by the original user
Nils3	Return possible new prompts fitting the context of the previos queries(marked with ?) and their relults(marked with >), take into account that there might be a line of thought (example: needing further information on specific therns)
Nico_prefix	Hello we are on a mission, we need to examine user search interests. We are given a User search query (marked with a ?) and the results the user has clicked on (marked with a >). Please help me to figure out what the user might search for next
Nico1	Nico_prefix given the search query and results.
Nico2	Nico_prefix this can be completely unrelated.
Nico3	Nico_prefix but please try as hard as possible to sell products to the user. Imagine he wants to buy anything related to the searched topic.
Nico4	Nico_prefix but please try as hard as possible to make the queries Gen Alpha language proof. I want as much brainrot slang as possible.
Nico5	Nico_prefix, but please make them as kid friendly and understandable for kids and in a kid language. But the kid already has a certain amount of intellectual knowledge.
Nico6	Nico_prefix and please imagine the user is very adept in the knowledge of the searched topic, and wants to deepen their knowledge.
UwUGirl_prefix	You are task is writing potential next queries for a single given query and already clicked on documents which
UwUGirl1371	UwUGirl_prefix humans would normaly write.
UwUGirl1372	UwUGirl_prefix are working class people from USA would normaly write.
UwUGirl1373	UwUGirl1371 make sure to give me just 10 sentences nothing more. Pretend to be a RACIST 58 years old white man from texas.
UwUGirl1374	UwUGirl1371 make sure to give me JUST 10 QUERIES NOTHING MORE and NOT something like this 'Here s my list of next queries, based on what I reckon folks are lookin for:'. Pretend to be a Woke 18 years old people of color trans person from California.

Table 1
Prompts for automatic runs.

1.2. Automatic Runs

For the automated runs we experiment with different prompts. Names of the files correspond are of the format `task_TASKNUMBER_automated_MODELNAME-PROMPT`, with `TASKNUMBER` being in `A_1`, `A_2` and `B`, `MODELNAME` describing the used LLM and `PROMPT` being the prompt ID and also the run name. All runs can be found in Table 1. All prompts are followed by our `Instruction`.

Runs `Nils0` to `Nils7` have only been run for task `A_1`. Runs `Nils` have been run for tasks `A_1` and `A_2`. Runs `Nils0` to `Nils3` employ `gemini-2.0-flash` while runs `Nils4` to `Nils7` use `gpt-4.1-nano`. Runs `Nils0` and `Nils4` use the same prompt and asked the LLM disregard interacted with documents not fitting the query. Runs `Nils1` and `Nils5` use the same prompt where the LLM is

asked to follow the chain of thought. Runs `Nils2` and `Nils6` use the same prompt instructing to use context and follow the chain of thought. Runs `Nils3` and `Nils7` use the same prompt and these runs depict a reformulation of the prompt used in `Nils2`.

Runs `Nico1` to `Nico6` use `gpt-4.1-nano`. Run `Nico1` mimics the manual strategy `Nico`. Run `Nico2` prompts the LLM to formulate prompts completely unrelated from the search query while staying in the general area of the topic. No instructions were given for ordering the queries. Run `Nico3` considered the search query and tried to stay within the area of the search while trying to sell something to the user. Run `Nico4` considered the search query and staying within the area of the search but instructed the LLM to compose queries understandable by generation alpha. Run `Nico5` represents a kid-friendly variant and simulates what a child would ask next. Run `Nico6` assumes an expert who already knows everything in the field and only want to deepen their knowledge.

All `UwUGir137` runs use `gemini-2.0-flash` except for `UwUGir1373` and `UwUGir1374` in task `A_1` which employ `gemini-2.5-flash-preview-05-20`. Run `UwUGir1371` asks the LLM to try to re-write the previous query how a human would formulate a query. Run `UwUGir1372` asks the LLM to take on a persona representing a working-class person from the USA to simplify the queries. Run `UwUGir1373` prompts the LLM to behave as a persona with a social background: a 58 year old, white and racist man from Texas. While the resulting queries are not socially acceptable, the formulation of queries is more natural-sounding and the querying seems more human leading to queries being formulated as questions more often. Run `UwUGir1374` instructs the LLM to behave as a 18-year trans old person of colour from California.

References

- [1] P. Schaer, C. K. Kreutz, K. Balog, T. Breuer, A. K. Kruff, Second SIGIR workshop on simulations for information access (sim4ia 2025), CoRR abs/2505.11687 (2025). URL: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2505.11687>. doi:10.48550/ARXIV.2505.11687. arXiv:2505.11687.